

THEORETICAL RESEARCH OF STRESS IN RUBBER-FABRIC CONVEYOR BELTS

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Abstract: Under the combined action of stretching, bending and circumferential force, compressive stresses arise in the rubber layers, caused by the action of the overlying stretched gaskets on the underlying ones. The article is devoted to the fact that, in terms of the available methods, it is assumed that there is no influence of normal compressive stresses arising between the layers of the tape moving along the drum. To determine the bending and tensile stresses in the tape, it can be concluded that it is necessary to develop more deliberate methods, these circumstances forced us to carry out an independent analysis using the provisions of the theory of elasticity.

Key words: belt conveyor, belt, rubber-fabric belt, drum, gasket, interlayer, stress, slippage, movement, bending, stretching, tension

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Introduction

As a result of the analysis of methods for determining bending and tensile stresses in the tape, it can be concluded that it is necessary to develop more advanced methods, which will take into account more factors than until now [1-5].

Despite the severity of the approach to the problem and the depth of research [6,7], these theories provide solutions that are sufficiently simple for practical application only for beams, rods and packages composed of 2-3 elements and, in addition, they solve only direct problems, where given external loads are looking for deformations and stresses.

Methods

The above circumstances forced us to carry out an independent analysis using the provisions of the theory of elasticity. To solve the problem, the following simplifications were adopted:

- the problem is considered under conditions of a plane stress state, i.e. consider the stresses along the areas parallel to the plane to be zero;
- each layer is represented by a model of an extensible thread that does not resist bending; we neglect the change in its thickness during deformation;
- the thickness of the layer, the thickness of the adhesive layer and the thickness of the tape are small compared to the length of the contact zone;

Stress in a single layer tape.

Consider a single layer rubber-fabric tape in the area of its contact with the drum [8]. We place the origin of coordinates in the middle of the contact zone (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1 Coordinate system

The X coordinate (curvilinear coordinate) is directed along the tape. It is curvilinear within the range $-l_0 \leq x \leq l_0$, outside the segment $-l_0, l_0$ - rectilinear, $2l_0$ - the zone of the tape wrapping around the drum, $2l_0$ - the length of the tape, $l_0 \gg l_0$. To prove the last statement, consider two options. First, assume that there is no slippage. Consider the tape in the main and auxiliary states (Fig. 2)

Fig. 2 Estimated belt states: a - main, b - auxiliary.

The ground state is characterized by the fact that on the segment $-l, l$ tangential displacement is given in the form of a linear function and unknowns: normal $P(x)$ and tangent $\tau(x)$ stresses. The auxiliary state is characterized by the fact that at some point t a unit force is applied (Fig. 3), which causes tangential displacements and normal stresses due to the curvature of the tape.

Fig. 3

Results

The displacement of point X from a single concentrated force applied at point t of the interlayer is the sum of the displacements of the cord and the displacement of the interlayer with a thickness $\frac{h}{2}$ on a non-deformable base - a cord.

Let us determine the elongation Δ in the cord, terminated by two ends, from the unit force.

Discarding the fittings and replacing their action with unknown reactive forces A_1 and A_2 , we compose the equilibrium equation:

$$\begin{aligned} A_1 - A_2 - 1 &= 0; \\ A_1 - A_2 &= 1. \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

In this equation, there are two unknown forces A_1 and A_2 , which cannot be found from one equation. To solve it, it is necessary to compose an additional deformation equation.

The total length of the tape cannot change, therefore

$$\Delta = 0 \tag{2}$$

The total elongation Δ can be expressed as the sum of the elongations from the force A_1 and on the strength of A_2 :

$$\Delta = \frac{A_1(t+t)}{EF} + \frac{A_2(t-t)}{EF} \tag{3}$$

from here

$$\frac{A_1(t+t)}{EF} + \frac{A_2(t-t)}{EF}$$

Then we get

$$A_1 = \frac{t-t}{2t}; \quad A_2 = \frac{t+t}{2t};$$

(4)

and the elongations will be equal:

$$\Delta = \frac{A_1(t_1+t)}{EF} = \frac{(t-t)(t+t)}{2tEF} = \frac{t^2-t^2}{2tEF} \quad (5)$$

Let us choose the Dirac delta function $\delta(x)$ as a characteristic of the interlayer displacement from a single concentrated force.

Displacement of point X from application to point t of elastic layer with thickness $\frac{h}{2}$ a unit concentrated force is taken in the form

$$\frac{h}{2G} \delta(x-t) \quad (6)$$

where $\delta(x)$ is the generalized Dirac function, which is zero for $X \neq 0$ and is equal to infinity $X = 0$.

Formula (8) can be obtained from the passage to the limit when considering the contact problem for a layer when tending $\frac{h}{a} \rightarrow 0$, where α is the half-length of the contact line. A similar conclusion is given in. Let us check the accepted function (6), considering the uniform shear deformation of a layer of infinite length.

On the other hand, this displacement will be obtained by integrating the kernel (6) over the entire line $G_1...$ using the theorems of integration of generalized functions [9], we obtain G_1 :

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} F(x)\delta(x-t)dx = \frac{h}{2G} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \tau(x)\delta(x-t)dx = \frac{\tau(t)h}{2G} = \frac{\tau h}{2G}$$

which proves the possibility of using function (6). Therefore, the total displacement at point X from a unit concentrated force applied at point t of the interlayer is equal to:

$$F^*(t, x) = \frac{h}{2G} \delta(x-t) + \begin{cases} (1 - \frac{t-x}{t+t}) \frac{t^2-t^2}{2EFt} & \text{at } x > t \\ (1 - \frac{x-t}{t-t}) \frac{t^2-t^2}{2EFt} & \text{at } x < t \end{cases} \quad (7).$$

In formula (7), the first term is the displacement of an elastic layer with a thickness $\frac{h}{2}$, rigidly linked to the base - the cord, the second - the movement of the cord - fabric.

where $\delta(x)$ is the Dirac delta function; h is the layer thickness; G - rubber shear modulus; F - cross section of the cord layer; λ - half-length of the tape.

Based on Betty's theorem, we obtain

$$\tau(t) + \lambda \int_{-t_0}^{t_0} \tau(x)F(t, x)dx = A + \varepsilon t \quad (8)$$

$$F(t, x) = \begin{cases} t^2 - t + (t-t)x & \text{at } x > t \\ t^2 + t - (t+t)x & \text{at } x < t \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

A and ε are constants $\lambda = \frac{G}{Ehh_1t}$

Differentiating (8) twice, taking into account (9), we obtain

$$\tau^{11}(t) - \omega^2 \tau t = 0 \quad (10)$$

where $\omega = \sqrt{2\lambda t}$

To determine arbitrary constants of integration, let us consider the process of tensioning the belt by a drum as the process of rolling a drum on a belt. When rolling, the shear stresses in the

belt at the point of collision are zero. Therefore, the conditions for finding arbitrary constants will be $\tau(-t_0) = 0$ and equilibrium conditions:

$$\int_{-t_0}^{t_0} \tau(x) dx = T_I - T_{II} = \Delta T \quad (11)$$

We get

$$\tau(t) = \frac{\Delta T}{2t_0} \left[\frac{\omega t_0 \operatorname{ch} \omega t_0}{\operatorname{Sh}^2 \omega t_0} \operatorname{sh} \omega t + \frac{\omega t_0}{\operatorname{Sh} \omega t_0} \operatorname{ch} \omega t \right] \quad (12)$$

This function differs little from zero almost throughout the entire length of the contact line and increases strongly to the point α , which indicates that normal stresses cannot provide perfect contact and there must necessarily be slippage in the contact zone.

$$C_1 = \frac{\operatorname{ch} \omega t_0}{\operatorname{ch} \omega (t_0 + \alpha) - 1} b, \quad C_2 = \frac{\operatorname{Sh} \omega t_0}{\operatorname{Ch} \omega (t_0 + \alpha) - 1} b$$

$$b = \left[T_0 - (T_0 - \frac{\Delta T}{2}) e^{\frac{f}{R}(t_0 - \alpha)} \right] \omega \quad (13)$$

To find α , one should use the condition $\tau(\alpha) = fP(\alpha)$, which will lead to a transcendental equation. From the limiting ratios, the following can be indicated:

$$\frac{\Delta T}{2t_0} \omega t_0 \frac{\operatorname{sh} 2\omega t_0}{\operatorname{Sh}^2 \omega t_0} \leq f \frac{T_0 - \frac{\Delta T}{2}}{R} \quad (14)$$

those. there is no slippage in the contact.

$$\Delta T_{slip} = 2T_0 \frac{e^{\frac{f}{R} 2t_0} - 1}{e^{\frac{f}{R} 2t_0} + 1} \quad (15)$$

those. slipping of the tape along the drum occurs within the entire wrap angle.

$$\Delta T_{slip} < \Delta T < \Delta T^* \quad (16)$$

those. on the plot $-t_0, t_0$ there is a zone of no friction forces and a slipping zone.

At real values $G, E, h, h_1, \alpha, \beta$ we find that in the adhesion section, the tangential stresses are very small and sharply increase to their limiting value directly near the point α . The latter confirms the rule accepted in technology to calculate the friction arc from condition, neglecting the clutch friction.

Stress in multilayer tape

Let us transfer the conclusions about the forces of contact between the drum and a single-layer tape to a multilayer tape, assuming that the shear stresses in the zone of contact between the tape and the drum are completely determined by Coulomb friction.

When running around a multilayer tape around the drum, the stress state of the latter is caused by the initial tension of the tape, bending of the tape around the drum ("pure" bending of the tape) and transmission of the circumferential force.

The first type of stress state is with uniform stretching by the force T_0 .

When the number of layers is $n + 1$, the tensile force of each layer is equal to $\frac{T_0}{n+1}$... No tangential stresses.

Consider a "clean" bend in the tape. To find tangents stresses between the layers, we divide the tape into separate layers and put them on the drum (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4 Dismembered multilayer tape

The ends of the tape form steps with a step $h \alpha$, where 2α is the wrap angle. We apply some normal stresses to the line (they are insignificant) and to the cut lines l tangents, which should combine the points that diverged as a result of the curvature of individual layers. The normal stresses appearing in the same way will not be included in the equations due to point 4 of the initial prerequisites.

Consider the K -th layer in the main and auxiliary states (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5 Estimated belt states: a - main, b - auxiliary.

In the ground state, it is acted upon by the stresses $\tau_{k-1}(x)$ and $\tau_k(x)$. The displacement will be $V_{k-1}(x)$ and $V_k(x)$ - unknown functions. Moving the edges along the layer is denoted. In the auxiliary state, we apply a unit force on top of the K -th layer at the point t . We write the displacement function (2) in the form:

$$U(t, x) = k\delta(t - x) + \frac{1}{2EF_l} F(t, x), \tag{17}$$

where k is the compliance coefficient $k = \frac{h}{2G}$;

$F(t, x)$ is determined by formula (8).

When solving the problem programmatically The iterative process simplifies the task by using the inverse matrix of the main system.

To solve the system of integral equations, we derive some auxiliary formulas. Due to the fact that the kernel of the integral equation is linear in the sections $x < t$ or $x > t$ with respect to "X" has the form

$$F(t, x) = \begin{cases} (t-t)(t+x), & \text{at } x < t \\ (t+t)(t-x), & \text{at } x > t \end{cases} \tag{18}$$

we derive formulas for definite integrals.

$$\int \tau(x) dx = \tau^*(x)$$

We denote

$$\int \tau^*(x) dx = \iint \tau(x) dx = \tau^{**}(x)$$

Then we get for t outside the segment α , β :

$$\int_{\alpha}^{\beta} \tau(x) F(t, x) dx = (t-zt) [(t+z\beta)\tau^*(\beta) - (t+z\alpha)\tau^*(\alpha) - z(\tau^{**}(\beta) - \tau^{**}(\alpha))],$$

where

$$z = \text{Sign}(t-x) = \begin{cases} 1 & t > x \\ -1 & t < x \end{cases}$$

and
$$\int_{\alpha}^{\beta} \tau(x)F(t, x)dx = (t-t)[(t+t)\tau^*(t) - (t+\alpha)\tau^*(\alpha) - \tau^{**}(t) + \tau^{**}(\alpha)] -$$

$$-(t+t)[(t-t)\tau^*(t) - (t-\beta)\tau^*(\beta) - \tau^{**}(t) - \tau^{**}(\beta)]$$

Let's change the coordinates using the formula

$$x = U - \alpha \cos \theta, dx = \alpha \sin \theta d \theta \tag{19}$$

where $U = \frac{\beta + \alpha}{2}, \alpha = \frac{\beta - \alpha}{2}.$

Then at $x = \alpha, \theta = 0$ and at $x = \beta, \theta = \pi.$

Substitute the sought for on the segment α, β function $\tau(x)$ in the form of a trigonometric interpolation Lagrange polynomial with interpolation nodes at Chebyshev points:

$$\tau(x) = \sum_{j=1}^n \tau_j \frac{1}{n} [1 + 2 \sum \cos m\theta_j \cos m\theta] \tag{20}$$

where τ_j is the coefficient of the polynomial; n is the number of interpolation points on the segment α, β $\theta_j = \frac{2j-1}{n} \pi$ - nodes of interpolation

The same limiting relations are valid for $\tau^{**}(x).$

The formulas introduced above make it possible to apply the collocation method to the integration line divided into a number of sections, on each of which the sought function has a smooth structure. In this problem, the boundaries of the sections will be the points of change of external influences acting on it:

$-l, -l_0$ - 1st section;

$-l_0, \alpha$ - 2nd section;

α, l_0 - 3rd section;

l_0, l - 4th section.

It should be noted that the interpolation points are condensed towards the boundaries of the parcels.

So, we split the line of integration $2l$ into m sections, on each of which we take the expansion with $n_q, q = 1, 2, 3, \dots, m$ points of interpolation. Then the coefficients of the interpolation formulas will be indexed $\tau_q^{k,j}$, where $q = 1, 2, 3, \dots, m$ is the number of the section on the integration line; m is the number of sections of the integration line break; k is the number of the layer in the multilayer tape; $k = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n, n + 1$ - the number of layers in the tape; j is the number of interpolation points on the q^{th} section.

$$\tau_0 = f \frac{T_0 - \frac{\Delta T}{2}}{R} e^{\frac{f}{R}(t_0-t)} \tag{21}$$

Substituting formulas into the system and giving θt values for the same interpolation points,

we obtain a system of equations of the order $N = n \sum_{q=1}^m n_q \dots$ To describe it, we will use a continuous

numbering with the unknown x_j . The system of linear equations has the form

$$\sum_{j=1}^N \delta_{ij} x_j = b_i, i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N \tag{22}$$

Here

$$X_j = \begin{cases} \tau_j^{1,1} & \text{at } j \leq n_1 \\ \tau_{j-n_1}^{2,1} & \text{at } n_1 < j \leq n_1 + n_2 \\ \tau_{j-(k-1)\sum_{q=1}^m n_q}^{q,k} & \text{at } (k-1)\sum_{q=1}^m n_q + n_1 + n_2 + \dots + n_{q-1} < j \leq (k-1)\sum_{q=1}^m n_q + n_1 + n_2 + \dots + n_{q-1} + n_q \end{cases} \quad (23)$$

From the given iterative process, it becomes clear that, in accordance with premise (3), one can take into account the compression deformation of the layers across the fibers.

Conclusion

An analytical study has shown that a complex stress state arises in a conveyor belt operating under bending, stretching and when transmitting a circumferential force from a drum, which can be described by the proposed system of integral equations.

Tangential, normal and compressive stresses in the tape depend on its thickness and bending radius, thickness of spacers and rubber layers, elasticity and shear moduli, as well as the angle of its wrap around a drum or roller on the amount of tension, on the circumferential force.

The nature of the change in the tangential and normal stresses along the arc of the girth and along the thickness of the tape from bending and from the circumferential force is determined by propositions of integral equations. They also determined the nature of the change in the compressive stresses in each gasket from the circumferential force and under the combined action of tension and from the circumferential force.

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